

Legal Risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Mapping Research Topics Using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Literature Review

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the development of research around legal risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The research was conducted from 1997 to 2022, by searching national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Scopus, and WoS via the Perish/Harzing application, with the keyword "Legal Risk". Based on the search results, there were 94 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a literature review study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to legal risk is divided into 7 clusters. Meanwhile, based on the results of a literature review study, there are 6 main themes related to legal risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

Keywords: Legal Risk, Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

INTRODUCTION

The development of risk management in financial institutions has increased in line with the development of the financial industry as a whole. In recent years, financial institutions have begun to understand the importance of risk management to maintain business stability and continuity. This can be seen from the existence of regulations from the Financial Services Authority (OJK) which regulate management risk exposure and effective corporate governance. Risks in the financial industry must be detected and controlled by estimating the possibilities that will occur in the future, not when the risk has already occurred. Thus, a methodology for modeling risks that will occur in the future is very important so that policy makers can prepare strategic steps to deal with risks that will occur in the future. One of the risks that occur in the financial industry is legal risk. Legal risk management involves identifying, assessing, controlling and monitoring these risks over time to ensure that the bank remains stable and maintains its reputation.

In previous research, the development of legal risk in banking was influenced by various factors such as changes in laws and regulations, legal demands from customers, and business changes in the banking industry. Banks must ensure that they comply with applicable regulations and manage legal risks well to avoid costly lawsuits. In the current digital era, banks must also pay attention to legal risks related to privacy and data security, as well as protecting customers from cyber crime. Banks today must ensure that they comply with regulations regarding the protection of personal data and customer privacy, as well as meeting security requirements in online transactions. In an increasingly competitive banking industry, banks must also ensure that they do not infringe on the intellectual rights or trademarks of others. Legal risks also include legal claims from customers who feel they have been harmed by the products or services provided by the bank. Therefore, banks must be careful in providing information and carrying out transactions with customers to avoid detrimental lawsuits. Thus, banks must always monitor developments in legal risk and ensure that they have an effective risk management system to overcome existing legal risks. Banks must also have an experienced internal legal team and have good relationships with external parties such as legal consultants to ensure that they can provide effective legal support if necessary. In complex or controversial situations, banks must also ensure that they have access to accurate legal information and analysis to make wise decisions.

Based on the problems above, mapping of legal risk management topics is needed to identify, measure and control risks that will occur. This can fulfill the need for human resources tasked with risk management to have knowledge, skills and work attitudes according to the bank's needs. So, the aim of this research is to map research topics around legal risks in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions using: (1) the VOSviewer bibliometric method to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field by creating a metadata network map; and (2) literature

review study to analyze, identify and review articles from indexed international journals and accredited national journals.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Legal risk is a risk caused by deficiencies in legal aspects, such as lawsuits, incompatibility of legal regulations with bank activities or products, or problems with invalid contracts and guarantees. The main objective of Legal Risk Management is to ensure that the risk management process can minimize the negative impact of deficiencies in legal aspects, changes and/or incompatibility with legal regulations, and litigation processes.

Bibliometric studies are the application of mathematical and statistical methods to the publication of books, articles and other information media. The aim is to analyze and study maps of literature development in publications in a scientific field. And can also analyze simple productivity indicators in research with more sophisticated and multidimensional techniques based on quotes in articles. So that it can identify and map new (multidisciplinary) scientific and technological developments.

VOSviewer is a software tool for creating, exploring and visualizing metadata network maps. It can be concluded that this device has two main functions:

- (1) Create bibliometric maps based on metadata networks. This map can create a network of scientific publications, journals, researchers, institutions, countries, keywords that are available or not yet available. To build this network, bibliographic database files are needed, such as Web of Science, Scopus, Dimensions, Lens and PubMed Files. Or from reference management files, such as RIS, EndNote, RefWorks Files) by inputting them into the software VOSviewer. And you can also download data via API, such as Crossref API, OpenAlex API, Europe PMC API and several others; And
- (2) Visualize and explore bibliometric maps. VOSviewer provides three forms of visualization, namely network, overlay and density visualization. The visualization can be enlarged making it possible to explore the bibliometric map in detail and completely, even if it contains thousands of items.

Literature review is the process of analyzing and identifying research articles on a particular theme. With this process, the steps for reviewing articles from journals, final assignments and seminar proceedings can be systematic and structured.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object of the research is legal risk. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles on legal risks in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

The source of data collection comes from search for national and international journals indexed by Google Scholar, Sprott, and Scopus via the Perish/Harzing application. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel software, Mendeley Desktop, and VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the keyword " Legal Risk " in the entire year period (1997 -2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics research based on literature review studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Legal Risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

There are 94 international and national journals based on the results of data collection from the Perish/Harzing application during the period 1997 to 2022. There are 10 journals Scopus indexed

international. And there is 84 international and national journals are indexed by Sinta around legal risk research.

Journal publication data regarding Legal Risk by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
1997-1999	2	2005	1	2011	4	2017	8
2000	-	2006	1	2012	4	2018	6
2001	-	2007	1	2013	4	2019	6
2002	1	2008	9	2014	4	2020	8
2003	1	2009	4	2015	7	2021	6
2004	3	2010	3	2016	7	2022	8

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research Regarding Legal Risk in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Search results for articles on software Perish/Harzing are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around Legal Risk. Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Software visualization results VOSViewer is related to the research development map regarding legal risks in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions, there are 7 clusters and 70 topic items in the mapping, including the following:

- Cluster 1, red, consists of 21 topic items, namely: banking, banking industry, banking supervision, compliance risk, credit risk, credit risk assessment, credit risk model, customer, financial product, insurance, Iran, Islamic banking, legal aspect, legal client, legal framework, legal risk, legal risk management, operational risk, reputation risk, shariah risk, south africa.
- Cluster 2, green, consists of 17 topic items, namely: arrangement, bank Indonesia, bpr, commercial bank, covid, financial system, liquidity assistance, mechanism, service authority, pbi, pljp, regulation, rural bank, sharia liquidity assistance, systemic bank, uu no 2, uuppsk.
- Cluster 3, dark blue, consists of 13 topic items, namely: bank risk, banking risk, barclays bank v obrien, corporate governance, independent legal advice, law, legal environment, legal management, legal origin, massey v midland bank, moral hazard, relationship, risk management.
- Cluster 4, yellow, consists of 9 topic items, namely: banks, sharia banks, BRI, law, Indonesia, financing, legal management arrangements, reputation, legal risks.
- Cluster 5, purple, consists of 5 topic items, namely: bank guarantee, climate risk, independence, return, risk.

- Cluster 6, light blue, consists of 3 topic items, namely: credit risk ratio, deposit risk, legal reserve requirement.
- Cluster 7, orange, consists of 2 topic items, namely: debtors, legal protection.

Mapping Literature Review around Problems in Legal Risk

There are several findings in this research topic, including:

First, legal risks in Bank for International Settlements (BIS) documents. BIS is an organization that focuses on global monetary and financial policy issues. In BIS documents, the term “legal risk” refers to potential losses arising from legal or regulatory issues related to a bank's business. Legal risks can arise from various sources such as changing regulations, litigation, lawsuits, or unauthorized business practices. BIS focuses on these legal risks by monitoring and providing guidance to mitigate these risks and ensure good business practices in the banking industry.

Second, legal risks in bank credit agreements are closely related to customer protection. Legal risks can arise in various forms such as contracts that do not meet legal requirements, violations of banking regulations, and violations of other legal regulations. If legal risks are not properly identified and controlled, this can cause financial losses for banks and customers. To ensure customer protection, banks must ensure that credit agreements meet applicable legal requirements and ensure that credit agreements meet industry standards. Banks must also ensure that customers understand the credit agreement and ensure that customers understand how credit works and how credit affects the customer's finances. Banks must also ensure that procedures and tasks in implementing credit agreements meet industry standards and ensure banking integrity and reputation. Banks must report and monitor legal risks and ensure that necessary actions are taken to minimize risks.

Third, the implementation of credit restructuring in banking must be reviewed from legal risks because many things must be considered to ensure that the restructuring is carried out correctly and meets applicable legal requirements. Credit restructuring can give rise to legal risks such as violations of banking regulations, contracts that do not meet legal requirements, and violations of other legal regulations. To minimize legal risks, banks must ensure that credit restructuring procedures meet industry standards and applicable legal regulations. Banks must also ensure that customers understand credit restructuring and ensure that customers understand how credit restructuring affects customer finances. Banks must report and monitor legal risks and ensure that necessary actions are taken to minimize risks. Banks must also ensure that credit restructuring documents meet legal requirements and ensure that credit restructuring documents meet industry standards.

Fourth, legal risks can occur in online lending practices, due to the rules and regulations that apply to banking and financial institutions, as well as the protection of customer rights and data security. Here are some legal risks that may occur in online lending practices:

- (1) Customer data security, namely online loans, requires the collection and storage of customer personal data, which has the potential to be stolen by irresponsible parties. This creates legal risks for financial institutions that do not meet the data security standards set by regulations.
- (2) Customer protection: Customers may feel unprotected if they experience problems with online loans, for example due to problems with the loan process or due to late payments. This requires financial institutions to ensure that they meet customer protection regulations and standards.
- (3) Transparency and fairness: Online loans can have higher interest rates compared to traditional loans. This creates legal risks for financial institutions if the interest rates are not transparent and unfair to customers.
- (4) Policies and regulations: Financial institutions must comply with the rules and regulations that apply to online loans, such as regulations regarding personal data processing, customer protection and interest rates.

Fifth, the legal risk aspect in Mudharabah, Murabahah, Ijarah financing transactions and other contracts. This can be done by: (1) Ensuring that the agreements in these contracts comply with applicable legal requirements and ensuring that the mudharabah muqayyadah agreement documents are available and easily accessible; (2) Ensure that transactions in these contracts comply with applicable rules and regulations, such as banking regulations, tax regulations and other legal regulations; (3) Conduct legal risk analysis and create action plans to minimize legal risks; (4) Ensure that banking employees understand the applicable legal regulations and ensure that the procedures and tasks

implemented meet industry standards and ensure banking integrity and reputation; and (5) Report and monitor legal risks and ensure that necessary actions are taken to minimize risks.

Sixth, banks operating in customary law systems must ensure that they understand and comply with all the rules and regulations that apply in their legal environment. Customary law systems may differ from common law systems, so banks must ensure that they have a good understanding of the legal practices and regulations that apply in their environment. Legal risks for banks operating in customary law systems involve potential legal issues that may arise from their business activities, such as litigation, lawsuits, or changing regulations. Banks must monitor and manage these legal risks well so they can anticipate and address legal issues before they become bigger problems. Conformity is an important factor in legal risk management in banks operating in customary law systems. Banks must ensure that they have appropriate systems and procedures in place to ensure that they comply with all applicable rules and regulations. This includes conducting regular audits, ensuring that staff have appropriate training, and ensuring that all business documents and records are stored properly.

Mapping Literature Review around Legal Risk Mitigation

There are several findings in this research topic, including:

First, mitigating legal risks for borrowers in banking is important to ensure that borrowers understand the risks associated with the credit they receive and ensure that borrowers understand how these risks affect their finances. The following are several ways that can help borrowers mitigate legal risks: (1) Understand credit conditions, namely borrowers must understand credit conditions, including interest rates, payment terms and monthly payment amounts. This helps borrowers ensure that they understand the risks associated with the credit; (2) Read the documents carefully, that is, borrowers must read the credit documents carefully and ensure that they understand the terms and conditions of the credit; (3) Seek legal assistance, i.e. if borrowers are unsure about credit conditions, they can seek assistance from a lawyer to help them understand the risks associated with the credit; (4) Look for alternatives, namely if borrowers feel that the legal risks associated with credit are too great, they can look for alternatives, such as looking for other sources of funds or considering not taking out credit; and (5) Report and monitor legal risks, namely the borrower must report and monitor legal risks and ensure that necessary actions are taken to minimize risks.

Second, mitigating legal risks for brand rights as collateral for bank credit involves several steps to minimize the legal risks associated with using brand rights as collateral. The following are several examples of steps that can be taken to overcome these legal risks: (1) Verify brand rights, namely the bank must verify that the brand rights used as collateral have valid rights and are not in conflict with other brand rights; (2) Documentation, namely the bank must ensure that documentation of brand rights used as collateral is available and can be accounted for if necessary; (3) Protection of brand rights, namely the bank must ensure that the brand rights used as collateral are protected in accordance with applicable rules and regulations; (4) Ensure that brand rights can be renewed, namely the bank must ensure that the brand rights used as collateral can be renewed in accordance with applicable rules and regulations; (5) Protection against unauthorized use, namely the bank must ensure that the brand rights used as collateral are not used illegally by other parties.

Third, mitigating legal risks regarding credit insurance at banks. The following are several examples of steps that can be taken to overcome these legal risks: (1) Equal treatment for all customers, namely banks must ensure that the procedures and regulations that apply to credit insurance are the same for all customers, without discrimination; (2) Clear and transparent contracts, namely banks must ensure that credit insurance contracts are clear and transparent, and comply with applicable regulations; (3) Appropriate documentation, namely the bank must ensure that credit insurance documentation is available and can be accounted for if necessary; (4) Protection against unauthorized use, namely the bank must ensure that credit insurance is not used illegally by other parties; and (5) Valid agreement, namely the bank must ensure that the credit insurance agreement is valid and meets applicable regulations.

Mapping Literature Review around the Definition and Objectives of Legal Risk Management

First, the definition of legal risk, namely risks related to violations of law by banks or applicable legal regulations in carrying out their business. This includes violations of banking laws, statutory regulations, contracts and agreements, as well as legal claims from third parties. This legal risk can

cause financial losses for banks and reduce public trust in banks. Therefore, it is important for banks to understand and monitor applicable legal regulations and ensure that their business does not violate the law.

Second, the aim of legal risk management. The findings in this research topic are:

- (1) To identify, evaluate and manage legal risks that may occur in banking business activities. This objective can help banks to avoid potential lawsuits and ensure that the bank operates in a manner that complies with applicable laws and regulations.
- (2) Legal risk management also aims to assist banks in identifying potential problems and ensuring that the bank has appropriate procedures and practices to address these problems before they develop into larger problems.

Mapping Literature Review around Legal Risk Supervision

Findings in this research topic include:

First, the authority and responsibility of the Board of Commissioners, namely: (1) Overseeing risk management, namely the Board of Commissioners is responsible for ensuring that the bank has an effective and well-functioning legal risk management system; (2) Approving policies and procedures, namely the Board of Commissioners must approve policies and procedures related to legal risk management, including legal risk prevention and control procedures; (3) Reviewing and monitoring legal risks, namely the Board of Commissioners must monitor legal risks related to banking business and ensure that they have the information necessary to make appropriate decisions; (4) Ensuring compliance, namely the Board of Commissioners must ensure that the bank complies with applicable laws and regulations, as well as ensuring that the legal risk management system ensures compliance; and (5) Providing guidance and support, namely the Board of Commissioners must provide guidance and support to management to ensure that the bank operates in a manner that complies with applicable laws and regulations.

Second, the authority and responsibility of the Board of Directors, namely: (1) Setting the legal risk management strategy, which is responsible for establishing a legal risk management strategy that is appropriate to the banking business and ensuring that the strategy is implemented effectively; (2) Implementing legal risk management policies and procedures, namely ensuring that legal risk management policies and procedures are implemented properly and in accordance with applicable regulations; (3) Monitoring and reporting legal risks, namely monitoring and reporting legal risks related to the banking business to the Board of Commissioners and taking the necessary actions to overcome these risks; (4) Ensuring compliance with laws and regulations, namely ensuring that the bank complies with applicable laws and regulations, as well as ensuring that the legal risk management system ensures compliance; and (5) Providing guidance and support to business units, namely providing guidance and support to business units to ensure that they understand and comply with legal risk management policies and procedures.

Third, related to Human Resources, namely: (1) Legal experts, namely banks must employ legal experts to assist in managing and overcoming legal risks; (2) Risk management teams, namely banks must have a risk management team responsible for monitoring and managing legal risks; (3) Business units, namely business units play an important role in managing legal risk; (4) Compliance teams, namely banks must employ a compliance team to ensure that the bank complies with applicable laws and regulations; and (5) Employees, namely all banking employees must understand the importance of legal risk management and comply with applicable policies and procedures.

Fourth, related to the Legal Risk Management Organization/OMRH. This organization aims to ensure that banks comply with applicable laws and regulations and manage legal risks effectively. The organizational structure of legal risk management varies from bank to bank, but generally includes several units or departments such as: (1) Legal unit, namely the unit responsible for providing legal advice and ensuring that the bank complies with applicable laws and regulations; (2) Risk management team, namely the team responsible for monitoring and managing legal risks at the bank; (3) Business unit, namely the unit responsible for ensuring that the bank's business operates in a manner that complies with applicable laws and regulations; (4) Compliance team, namely the team responsible for ensuring that the bank complies with applicable laws and regulations; and (5) the Board of Commissioners and the Board of Directors, who have final responsibility for ensuring that the bank complies with applicable laws and regulations and ensuring that legal risk management operates effectively.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Strategy, Risk Level, Policies, Procedures and Limits in Legal Risk Management

First, legal risk management strategy. Findings in this research topic include:

- (1) Development and implementation of legal procedures, namely banks must have clear and effective legal procedures to overcome legal risks. This includes establishing clear legal standards for transactions and ensuring that each transaction meets applicable legal requirements.
- (2) Review, evaluation of contracts and documents, namely banks must periodically review and evaluate contracts and documents issued by the bank to ensure that they meet applicable legal requirements.
- (3) Staff training and education, namely banks must provide training and education to their staff about legal issues related to bank operational activities, including how to overcome legal risks.
- (4) Placement of legal staff, namely the bank must place legal staff who have knowledge and experience in the legal field related to the bank's operational activities. These staff should be responsible for ensuring that the bank meets applicable legal requirements.
- (5) Monitoring and evaluating legal developments, namely banks must monitor and evaluate applicable legal developments to ensure that the bank meets applicable legal requirements.
- (6) Collaboration with legal consultants, namely banks must collaborate with legal consultants who have experience in the legal field related to bank operational activities. These consultants should assist the bank in dealing with legal risks that may arise.

Second, the level of risk to be taken (Risk Appetite) and risk tolerance (Risk Tolerance). Risk appetite is the amount of risk that a company or individual is prepared to take in achieving its goals. In terms of legal risk in banking, risk Appetite will determine the extent to which the bank is prepared to take legal risks in conducting its business, for example by expanding the range of products and services or by entering new markets. Meanwhile, risk tolerance refers to how much risk a company or individual can accept before starting to feel uncomfortable. In terms of legal risk in banking, risk tolerance will determine how much legal risk a bank can accept before it affects their business decisions and reputation. These two terms are important in understanding and managing legal risk in banking, as they help banks to determine the extent to which they are prepared to take risks and how much impact is acceptable on their business and reputation.

Third, legal risk policy. The following are several legal risk policies commonly used by banks:

- (1) Compliance policy, namely banks will ensure that they comply with all laws and regulations that apply to their business;
- (2) Risk control policy, namely the bank will implement an adequate risk control system to monitor and minimize legal risks;
- (3) Policy for handling legal claims, namely the bank will have clear procedures for handling legal claims, including ensuring that they have access to quality legal services;
- (4) Training and education policy, namely banks will provide training and education for their employees about legal risks and how to manage these risks; and
- (5) Monitoring and evaluation policies, namely banks will monitor and evaluate their policies and procedures to ensure that they are effective in managing legal risks.

Fourth, legal risk procedures. The following are several legal risk procedures commonly used by banks: (1) Legal risk identification, namely banks will evaluate their business and activities to determine the sources of legal risk; (2) Risk analysis, namely the bank will evaluate the level of legal risk and potential impacts associated with each source of risk; (3) Action planning, namely the bank will determine the actions to be taken to manage and minimize legal risks; (4) Implementation, namely the bank will implement planned actions to manage legal risks; (5) Monitoring and evaluation, namely the bank will monitor and evaluate the actions taken to ensure that they are effective in managing legal risks; and (6) Procedure updates, namely banks will update their procedures in accordance with business developments and the legal environment.

Fifth, legal risk limits. Legal risk limits in banking are certain limits or capacities set by banks to take legal risks. This limit is usually set based on the bank's risk tolerance level and ensures that the bank does not take excessive legal risks. The following are several legal risk limits in banking: (1) Limit on the number of lawsuits, namely the bank will set a certain limit for the number of lawsuits received within a certain time period; (2) Limit on the amount of legal losses, namely the bank will set a certain limit for the amount of legal losses that may occur within a certain time period; (3) Risk level limits,

namely banks will set certain limits for the level of legal risk that is acceptable in their business; and (5) Legal expenses limit, namely the bank will set a certain limit for legal expenses, such as legal fees or fines.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Legal Risk Identification, Measurement, Monitoring, Control and Information Systems

First, identify legal risks, including: (1) Regulatory analysis, namely banks must ensure that they understand the regulations and regulations that apply to the banking industry and carry out regular regulatory analysis to ensure that they comply with applicable regulations; (2) Contract analysis, namely the bank must ensure that all contracts made comply with applicable laws and regulations; (3) Due diligence, namely banks must carry out due diligence on customers and third parties before starting business with them; (4) Monitoring customers and transactions, namely banks must ensure that they monitor customers and transactions regularly to ensure that they comply with anti-money laundering and terrorism prevention regulations; (5) Legal risk management, namely the bank must have a legal risk team that ensures that the bank understands and addresses legal risks that may occur; (6) Data analysis, namely banks must ensure that they have adequate systems to monitor and analyze business data and information to ensure that they understand and address possible legal risks; and (7) Outreach and training, namely banks must carry out outreach and training to employees and customers about legal risks and how to overcome them.

Second, measuring legal risk. Measuring legal risk in banking is a process for determining and assessing risks associated with legal banking activities. In the banking industry, legal risks can originate from a variety of sources, including rules and regulations, litigation, and third party actions. To measure legal risk in banking, several steps that can be taken are: (1) Identify sources of legal risk, namely the first step in measuring legal risk is to identify sources of risk, such as rules and regulations, litigation, and third party actions; (2) Risk assessment, namely after the source of risk is identified, the bank must assess the legal risks that may occur and determine the level of risk; (3) Determining the level of risk tolerance, namely the bank must determine the level of risk tolerance in accordance with its business strategy and objectives; (4) Developing strategies to overcome risks, namely banks must develop strategies to overcome legal risks, such as risk management, insurance and regulatory monitoring; and (5) Monitoring and evaluation, namely the final step is monitoring and evaluating the performance of strategies to overcome legal risks and make necessary changes.

Third, monitoring legal risks, namely:

- (1) Monitoring legal risk in banking is a process that involves identifying, evaluating and controlling legal risks that may occur in the banking business. Legal risks are risks originating from applicable regulations, rules and laws, as well as from third party actions such as lawsuits.
- (2) To monitor legal risks, banks usually implement appropriate governance, establish procedures and internal control systems, and determine procedures and mechanisms for handling lawsuits and disputes. Banks also usually employ a legal team or employ legal consultants to assist in monitoring and managing legal risks.
- (3) Effective monitoring of legal risks is critical for banks as it can help reduce risks associated with lawsuits or disputes, as well as ensure that banks operate in accordance with applicable regulations and industry standards. This also helps maintain the bank's reputation and integrity, and ensures that the bank can continue to run its business efficiently and profitably.

Fourth, control legal risk. The following are several ways that can be done to control legal risk in banking: (1) Strong governance, namely banks must have strong and appropriate governance to ensure that they operate in accordance with applicable regulations and industry standards; (2) Internal Control Procedures and Systems, namely banks must have internal control procedures and systems to monitor and manage legal risks; (3) Legal teams and consultants, namely banks can employ legal teams or legal consultants to assist in monitoring and managing legal risks; (4) Training and education, namely banks must provide training and education about legal risks and good governance to their staff and leaders; (5) Monitoring and evaluation, namely the bank must carry out regular monitoring and evaluation to ensure that internal control procedures and systems function well and ensure that the bank operates in accordance with applicable regulations; and (6) Quick response and preventive action, namely banks must have a mechanism to handle legal claims and disputes quickly and effectively, as well as take preventive action to prevent legal risks from occurring. Effective legal risk control is very

important for banks because it can help reduce the risks associated with lawsuits or disputes, as well as ensure that the bank operates in accordance with applicable regulations and industry standards. This also helps maintain the bank's reputation and integrity, and ensures that the bank can continue to run its business efficiently and profitably.

Fifth, Legal Risk Management Information System. The Legal Risk Management Information System (Legal Risk Management Information System) is the technology used by banks to monitor and manage legal risks. These systems typically use databases and algorithms to collect and analyze legal information, helping banks make informed and data-driven decisions about how to manage legal risks. Several features of the Legal Risk Management Information System include: (1) Risk identification, namely a system that helps banks identify legal risks that may occur, such as lawsuits, disputes, or new regulations that may affect the bank's business; (2) Risk evaluation, namely a system that helps banks evaluate legal risks and prioritize the most significant risks; (3) Risk Monitoring, namely a system that helps banks monitor and monitor changes in legal risk in real-time; (4) Reporting and analysis, namely a system that assists banks in reporting and analyzing legal risks, as well as monitoring trends and patterns in legal risks; and (5) Documentation and document management, namely a system that helps banks manage legal documents and ensure that the necessary legal information is available and easy to access. Using a Legal Risk Management Information System can help banks increase efficiency and effectiveness in monitoring and managing legal risks. It also assists banks in ensuring that they comply with applicable regulations and industry standards, and helps maintain the bank's reputation and integrity.

Sixth, Legal Risk Internal Control System. The Legal Risk Internal Control System is a system used by banks to ensure that their businesses and operations comply with legal regulations and minimize legal risks. This system is part of a broader internal control system, and can consist of various procedures, tasks and technologies used to manage legal risks. Several features of the Legal Risk Internal Control System include: (1) Legal risk analysis, namely a system that helps banks evaluate legal risks and create action plans to minimize risks; (2) Procedures and tasks, namely a system that ensures that banks have clear procedures and tasks to manage legal risks, such as monitoring applicable legal regulations, ensuring that legal documents are available and easily accessible, and ensuring that employees understand applicable legal regulations; (3) Reporting and monitoring, namely a system that assists banks in reporting and monitoring legal risks, ensuring that legal risks are under control, and ensuring that necessary actions are taken to minimize risks; and (4) Documentation and document management, namely a system that helps banks manage legal documents and ensure that the necessary legal information is available and easy to access. The use of a Legal Risk Internal Control System helps banks ensure that their business and operations comply with legal regulations and minimize legal risks. It also helps banks in ensuring that they meet industry standards and maintain their integrity and reputation. This system can assist banks in ensuring that they comply with regulations and reduce the risk of lawsuits and disputes.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENTIONS

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding legal risks in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions during the period 1997 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 94 research articles.
- In the mapping visualization using the VOS viewer, the development of research regarding legal risks in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions is divided into 7 clusters and 70 items. Cluster 1 consists of 21 items, cluster 2 consists of 17 items, cluster 3 consists of 13 items, cluster 4 consists of 9 items, cluster 5 consists of 5 items, cluster 6 consists of 3 items, and cluster 7 consists of 2 items.
- Based on a literature review, there are 6 main research themes surrounding legal risks in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions, namely: (1) Risk issues; (2) Risk mitigation; (3) Definition and objectives of risk management; (4) Risk monitoring; (5) Strategy, risk level, policies, procedures, limits; and (6) Identification, measurement, monitoring, control, information systems.

Recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- The results of the e- review literature study can be explained in a more complex way.

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